

Effect of Supply Chain Drivers on Organization Performance. Evidence from Performance of Cement Manufacturing Firms in Kenya

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of supply chain drivers on the performance of Cement Manufacturing firms. A descriptive research design was used. The target population of the study was Managers or equivalent from Six (6) departments is Procurement, finance, legal, stores, human resource and quality control because they are directly concerned with the supply chain. The sample sizes were 83 respondents from a target population of 500. The study adopted the use of a questionnaire as the main research instrument. The study adopted both quantitative and qualitative approaches, implying that both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were employed. Quantitative data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS version 24). The study tested the significance level of each independent variable against the dependent variable at 95% confidence level using ANOVA, Correlation and regression techniques. The results revealed that commitment from the top management and lead to an effective collaboration between the firm and its suppliers. Furthermore, collaboration with the suppliers plays an instrumental role in reducing the lead time. Therefore, firms have to work collaboratively to serve the customers.

Keywords: *Top Management Support, Lead Time, Organization Performance, Supply Chain Drivers*

Introduction

According to the Global Supply Chain Forum, Supply Chain Management (SCM) is the integration of key business processes from end-user through original suppliers that provide products, services, and information that adds value for the customer and other stakeholders (Bergman & Klefsjo, 2010). SCM is a proactive relationship between a buyer and supplier and the integration is across the whole of the SC, not just first-tier suppliers (Cox et al., 2004). Most SCM-related challenges stem from either uncertainties or an inability to coordinate several activities and partners (Baiman & Rajan, 2012). The motive behind the formation of supply chain management is to increase channel competitive advantage (Tsiakis et al., 2011). (Fawcett & Magnan, 2012) defines two basic competitiveness or competitive advantage: cost leadership and differentiation. Improving a firm's competitiveness and profitability through supply chain management can be accomplished by enhancing overall customer satisfaction (Schein, 2014).

Supply chain management has become an important means of sustaining a competitive advantage for all successful industries and businesses (Sharafali, 2010). The objective of every supply chain is to maximize the overall value generated. The value a supply chain generates to an organization is the difference between what the final product is worth to the customer and the effort the supply chain expends in filling the customer's request. For most commercial supply chains, the value will be strongly correlated with supply chain profitability, the difference between the revenue generated from the customer and the overall cost across the supply chain (Huan, 2004).

The collaborative was cited for having been named the same as a partnership, closed, relational or collaborative (Lambert & Cooper, 2016). This category is characterized by relationships in which suppliers typically are subsidiaries or affiliates of the buyer (Arani et al., 2016). These relationships are based on having long term relationships with a few selected suppliers. Besides saving costs, collaborative relationships also aim to, among others, improve the ability to produce technologically sophisticated products and to

achieve more effective communication flow, more reliable delivery and better quality (Sahin & Robinson, 2012). The antecedents this relationship has been denoted by researchers to be commitment (Topan et al., 2012), trust, joint action and flexibility and specific transaction investments. Other authors categorized three different types of relationships after they had reviewed the numerous research works that had given between seven and eight varying relationship dimensions that could be explored: arm's length, cooperative relationships and integration. Arm's-length transactions neither provide time for personal relationships within the business framework nor do they require any shared trust or extensive personal communication beyond the transactions themselves (Musa, 2011). Co-operative relationships promote the sharing of knowledge, which is considered a source of competitive advantage. Integration describes the nature of SCM as it includes the entire value chain and performs each of the channel functions (Boyd & Gupta, 2014).

Cement Manufacturing is an important sector in Kenya and it makes a substantial contribution to the country's economic development. The Cement Manufacturing firms depend largely on their suppliers to avail of quality raw materials at the right time. In East Africa, Kenya is leading in both cement production and consumption. There are around 8 cement companies in Kenya. Three of these companies are listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange. Cement manufacturing companies that are listed at the NSE are Bamburi Cement, ARM Cement Limited and East Africa Portland Cement Company. Private companies are Mombasa Cement, National Cement and Savannah Cement. Dangote Cement and Lake Cement are slated to enter the market soon. The Cement manufacturing and Allied firms recorded in NSE incorporate; (NSE, 2013). This forms the target population and procurement, finance and Production staff will be target respondents. However, in many cases, supplier slackness and laxity in responding to buyers' needs have been a common occurrence characterized by increased lead times and cycle time. This has a negative impact on the buyers causing them to keep large buffer stock to cater to supplier uncertainty. Hence, it is paramount for firms to create Supply chain practices that boost the way suppliers respond to them. In addition, many researchers have focused on the supplier relationship subject leaning towards the buyer organizations' performance without looking at the influence of any relationship on how the suppliers will respond. In addressing the knowledge gap on supplier responsiveness subject, the researcher looked at the following variables in the Buyer-supplier relationship and how they relate to supplier responsiveness; Supplier positioning, nature of Supply chain practices, Information systems adoption in existing relationships and supplier development.

Cement companies attain significant savings from effective supply chain practices, which amount between 40%-45% of total costs (Okello & Were, 2014). Effective supply chain practices can lead to a reduction in cost, resulting in a significant saving. A potential 7% saving on total cost through effective inventory is achievable (Moinzadeh, 2011). Indeed, for many cement manufacturing firms inventory costs account for over 50 % of total production costs (Chen et al., 2014). Today, it is commonly accepted that the cost of inventory to a business is between 4% and 15% on top of the stock's value (PPOA, 2005). Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya are characterized by elongated or overextended chain retailers (buyers/agents), which, in turn, mean long chains of transactions between chain members and consumers (Ouyang et al., 2017). (World Bank, 2016) showed that leading cement manufacturing firms in Kenya are faced with problems of wrong forecasting due to an unavailability of enough supply chain practices data. In 2012 Athi River mining was affected by poor supply chain practices related cases leading to low performance (NSE, 2014). This caused erratic deliveries in these firms, late deliveries and inflexibility hence affecting customer satisfaction within their downstream chain (Kimani, 2013). Customers are concerned with the availability of the product and the ability of the firms to meet their needs timely (Gunasekaran, 2011).

Thus the study focuses on the role of supply chain practices on performance in the cement manufacturing sector in Kenya with reference to Portland Cement Ltd. These previous studies did not address the Cement Manufacturing sector and it is against this backdrop that this study was undertaken to look into the role of Supply Chain practices on performance of Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya

Literature Review

The study looks at the issues related to Supply Chain drivers and

Top management supply support

According to Chia, (2012) in research on management relationship and organizational performance, the study shows that 72.3% of respondents in Cement Manufacturing firms were using top management relationships. The research shows that the following factors have been adopted by many large Cement Manufacturing organizations to a large extent: Communication between company and suppliers, Trust between company and suppliers, Maintenance of long term relationships, Commitment between company and suppliers, Mutual information sharing between company and suppliers, Responsiveness to each other's needs and understanding of each other's roles and responsibilities. All of the above factors had 55% of the total respondent's views.

Research on the relationship between performance and management of supermarkets in Nairobi was viewed (Arani et al., 2016). The study focused on the respondent's response to how often suppliers meet delivery timelines. From the research findings, 79.2 % of the suppliers meet always, 20.8 % occasionally meet while there are no suppliers who do not meet their delivery timeliness. However, online ordering has not gained popularity; most suppliers do meet delivery timelines. Management relationships emerged during the early 20th Century in Japan (Nishiguchi, 2014). Excessive demand for parts of goods after World War I urged many companies to utilize suppliers following the temporary increase in productions (Pitamber & Dharup, 2014). In the 1960s and '70s, relationships were characterized by an adversarial, arm's -length approach suiting price-oriented buying. At the beginning of the '90s, relationships required an even greater degree of interaction due to the added need for product innovation and cooperation in technological developments, and this high level of interaction is termed partnership (Arani et al., 2016).

Firms compete in head-to-head battles for market share and position with other organizations in their competitive sets. Here suppliers are often treated in an adversarial manner by buyers, as the relationship between buyers and suppliers is viewed in a win-lose situation (Lambert & Cooper, 2016). It is imperative, therefore for firms to appreciate that supply chain relationships are not simple to cultivate and maintain collaborative efforts. The relationships should be for a strategic subset of suppliers and customers of the supply chain. These subsets of suppliers are firms that provide strategic products, or services, or who purchase large quantities of finished goods. This has brought about the concept of supplier positioning, where suppliers are classified in different categories based on the product value and risks (Sahin & Robinson, 2012).

However, many forward-looking firms have found it more effective to work collaboratively with their suppliers to serve the ultimate customer. Terms such as alliances, partnerships and collaborations have been used to describe these new buyer-supplier relationships (Sahin & Robinson, 2012). Recent trends to buy instead of make, to outsource instead of continuing to make, to improve quality, to lower inventories, to integrate supplier and purchaser systems and to create cooperative relations such as partnerships have underlined the need for outstanding performance and that calls for negotiation. For good supplier relationship management, the members of the internal team have to deal directly with their appropriate counterparts on the supplier side (Topan et al., 2012).

Lead Time

A closer and stronger relationship allow the channel members to achieve quality improvements, cost management and revenue growth. As well they provide the capability to deal with demand and supply uncertainties (Lee et al., 2007). The determination of the knowhow of supplier processes and the total cost

structure helps to develop supplier relationships (Arshinder et al., 2011). Effective supplier management can make the procurement process more cost and time-efficient. Having supply market intelligence and applying a correct competition situation are ways to implement a good supplier management strategy. Other issues that should be accounted for are a reliable source for supplier performance, evaluation and developing the suppliers. With the help of common procurement approaches and development projects, the supplier relationship is utilized to the maximum (Musa, 2011)

According to (Boyd & Gupta, 2014), lead time is the action taken in response to the relevant information generated and subsequently filtered between buyers and suppliers. They propose that a firm's responses need to be aligned with its customers' needs. A responsive organization knows how to execute its strategy and day-to-day options, make the constant adjustments to the customer, market and internal changes and thrive in an environment of dynamic competition. Responsive companies do not lag the market; rather, they act on decisions with focus, speed and scale. They know what they are, and more importantly, what they are not. As markets and technologies change, more and more rapidly, suppliers must respond quickly and frequently to strategic moves if they are to sustain competitive advantage (Cox et al. 2004). Hence, supplier responsiveness is a necessity for Cement Manufacturing firms.

The supplier positioning model is a way that businesses rank their sources of supplies based on the amount of money spent with the supplier and the level of vulnerability a business has if that supplier fails. According to (Sahin & Robinson, 2012), supply positioning is a process of measuring spend or profit impact via volume purchased, percentage of total cost and impact on product quality or business growth by supply risk via availability, number of suppliers, competitive demand, storage risks and substitution opportunities (Axsater, 2013). Many large companies specify which suppliers are to be used by their first-tier suppliers, mainly because particular critical components have to fit with other critical components (Arshinder et al., 2011).

Research Gaps

There has been a long-term problem with identifying value from the performance. In a study by Baiman & Rajan, (2012) on usage, obstacles and policies on supply chain practices show that only thirty three percent of sugar corporations have implemented supply chain practices as a strategy to improving performance which correctly is supported by (Axsater, 2013) who observed that ninety six percent of large cement manufacturing firms in Nairobi Kenya had adopted supply chain practices but at different level of maturity. Deuermeyer & Schwarz, (2011), while looking at the determinant of supply chain practices on performance in the tea sector, evaluated information sharing, partnership relation, and supplier integration and supplier appraisal. The study did not evaluate the cycle time reduction and cost-saving which need to be evaluated. It yet not clears whether the implementation of supply chain practices has impacted the performance of manufacturing firms and this study, therefore, will bridge this gap by examining the effect of supply chain practices on performance of cement companies in Kenya: a case of Portland cement ltd.

Material and Methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The target population of the study was managers or equivalent from five (5) departments that is Procurement, finance, human resource, operations and stores because they are directly concerned with the supply chain. According to records at the Portland, there are up to 1140 staff within these departments and this formed the target population. The sample of 92 respondents was used from the target population of 1140. The study used a questionnaire as the research instrument. The researcher also used Cronbach's Alpha to test the reliability of the proposed constructs. Qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The same method was used to summarize the dependent variable, as exhibited from the data collected from various investment clubs. Content analysis was used to

analyze qualitative data. A regression model was used to establish the effect of various on Performance through supply chain practices, detailed in the conceptual framework. The dependent variable was continuous but modeled into logistic outcomes as needed.

Multiple Regression Analysis Model

Performance at Portland was regressed against four variables as follows:

$$Y = a + B1x1 + B2x2 + \acute{\epsilon}$$

Ys = Performance

a = Constant (Co-efficient of intercept)

X1 = top management commitment ;

X2 =lead time

acute{\epsilon}= Error Term

B1B2= Regression co-efficient of four variables.

Results

This section presents and discusses the results of this study based on the formulated objectives and research questions, as presented in chapter one. The study findings revealed that the researcher distributed 92 questionnaires to the respondents.79 questionnaires out of the 92 were returned, which gives a response rate of approximately 85.87%. This response rate is above average. Even though the percentage rate of response was above average, the number of distributed questionnaires may have implications on the validity of the statistical analysis. The writer did, however, decide to continue with the analysis because the theoretical part of the project was already done.

Descriptive Statistics

From the findings in Table 1, respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the top management supply supports their supplier in product development. Furthermore, the findings show that firms help their supplier in employee training, while 13 (16.5%) disagree and were not sure of this, respectively giving a mean response of 4.13 (SD = 0.648). share some of the risks with their suppliers (3.46, SD = 1.01), ensure their suppliers have continuous improvement (3.80 (SD = 0.740) regarding the continuous improvement of the suppliers. Finally, the findings show that top management and their suppliers have improved Problem Solving (3.68, SD = 0.885). The overall mean response for top management supply support was 3.79 (SD = 0.384), indicating overall agreement by the majority of the employees regarding aspects of top management supply support. Assessment of the standard deviations shows that all of them are within the +/-1.96 range which is the approximate value of the 95 percentile point of the normal distribution.

Table 1: Top Management Supply Support

	Mean	SD
Top management support our supplier in product development	3.68	0.885
Top management help our supplier in employees training	4.13	0.648
Top management share some of the risks with our suppliers	3.46	1.010
Top management ensure our supplier have continuous improvement	3.80	0.740
The Top management and our suppliers we have improved Problem Solving	3.68	0.885

Lead time

Findings showed that the organization receives goods from suppliers only when they are required to eliminate waste ($M=3.85$, $SD=1.02$), revealing that the organization receives goods from suppliers only when they are required to eliminate waste. Findings also showed that the cost of the warehouse is reduced by the organization because of JIT, ensures high quality products are delivered on time, emphasis on the reduction of the replenishment lead time from suppliers. Besides, to find out whether every supplier makes a commitment to stock an inventory of approved stock, findings indicated that not every supplier makes a commitment to stock an inventory of approved stock.

Finally, results showed that the collaboration by suppliers had reduced the lead time. In a nutshell, the organization receives goods from suppliers only when they are required to eliminate waste, the cost of warehouse is reduced by the organization because of JIT, the organization ensures high quality products are delivered on time, there is emphasis on the reduction of the replenishment lead time from suppliers and collaboration by suppliers has reduced the lead time. However, not every supplier makes a commitment to stock an inventory of approved stock. The results on lead time summed up to a mean of 3.68 and a standard deviation of 0.83.

Table 2 *Lead Time*

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The organization receive goods from suppliers only when they are required to eliminate waste	3.85	1.02
The organization also reduces the cost of warehouse or storage due to JIT	3.68	1.04
The organization ensure high quality products are delivered in time	3.55	0.77
The organization managers highly focus on the reduction of the replenishment lead time from suppliers	3.54	1.00
Every supply makes a commitment to stock an inventory of approved stock	3.34	0.91
The organization decreasing lead times by supplier collaboration	3.69	1.01
Lead Time	3.68	0.83

Performance of the cement manufacturing sector

The study further sought to establish their perspectives on the performance of the cement manufacturing sector. This is because competitiveness is important for a firm because it increases performance. Competitiveness is gained when organizations perform better than their competitors in the same industry. The findings were presented in Table 1. The findings show that the company has preserved a high market share in the past two years (mean = 3.81, $SD= 0.880$), they have experienced high growth sales in the past two years, mean = 3.68 ($SD = 0.948$). Further, the findings also show that firms have been able to retain most of their customers in the past two years respectively (mean = 3.76, $SD = 0.788$). In addition, the findings show that firms have increased their market size in new markets in relation to their competitors (mean = 3.61, $SD = 0.846$), successfully created positive reputation, and increased perception of customer satisfaction The overall mean response was 3.76 ($SD = 0.667$) indicating that the level of performance of cement manufacturing sector has improved.

Table 3 Performance of cement manufacturing sector

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The company has preserved a high market share in the past two years	3.81	0.880
The company has experienced high growth sales in the past two years	3.68	0.948
The company has been able to retain most of our customers in the past two years	3.76	0.788
The company has increased our market size in new markets in relation to our competitors	3.61	0.846
The company has successfully created a positive reputation	3.97	0.975
The company has increased the perception of customer satisfaction	3.73	1.048
Performance	3.761	0.66797

Inferential Statistics

The findings in Table 4 show that management support has a positive and significant relationship with the performance of cement manufacturing firms, $\rho = 0.771$, $p < 0.001$. Finally, lead time has a positive and significant relationship with the performance of cement manufacturing firms, $\rho = 0.693$, $p < 0.001$. There are also significant inter-factor relationships that point to the fact that they are mutually dependent. The findings in Table 4 on the model summary show that all the predictors explain 68.2% of the variation in performance of cement manufacturing firms ($R = 0.826$, R -squared = 0.682, Adjusted R -squared = 0.664). The coefficient of determination explains the extent to which changes in the response variable can be explained by the change in the explanatory variables or the percentage of variation in the dependent variable that is explained by all the independent variables. ANOVA results in Table 4 show that the model fit was good, as illustrated by the overall test of significance with $F(4, 74)$ value of 39.607 with $p < 0.001$. Thus, the model was fit to predictors' performance of cement manufacturing firms based on cost management support, lead time.

From the findings in Table 4, management support has a positive and significant effect on performance, $\beta_1 = 0.379$, $p = 0.002$. This means that with each unit increase in management support, performance would increase by 0.379 units. Also, the findings in Table 4.14 show that lead time has a positive and significant effect on $\beta_2 = 0.226$, $p = 0.022$. This means that with each unit increase in lead time, performance would increase by 0.226 units. In line with these findings, Aragon (2003) indicated that timely and informative customer demand data could result in improved firm performance through reduced inventories. The results on top management supply support indicated that the top management supply supports its supplier in product development. The firm helps the suppliers in training employees and shares some of the risks with their suppliers. Companies ensure that their suppliers have continuous improvement. As well, the top management and their suppliers have improved problem solving.

Finally, findings on lead time showed that the organization receives goods from suppliers only when they are required to eliminate waste, the cost of warehouse is reduced by the organization because of JIT, the organization ensures high quality products are delivered on time, there is emphasis on the reduction of the replenishment lead time from suppliers and collaboration by suppliers has reduced the lead time. However, not every supplier makes a commitment to stock an inventory of approved stock.

Table 4: Regression model

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Correlation r
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
(Constant)	0.639	0.263		2.430	0.018	
management support	0.351	0.107	0.379	3.274	0.002	.771**
Lead time	0.205	0.088	0.226	2.334	0.022	.693**
R Square	0.682					
Adjusted R Square	0.664					
F	39.607					
Sig.	0.000					

a Dependent Variable: Performance

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Conclusion

Basing on the study findings, top management supply support provides and creates the needed conditions for improved performance of cement manufacturing firms. Concisely, commitment from the top management leads to an effective collaboration between the firm and its suppliers, while on the other hand, lack of it inhibits product development. Through top management supply support, employees are trained and problem solving is improved by both the top management and suppliers. Finally, lead time positively and significantly influences performance. The implication is that the procurement performance is improved in the event that high quality products are delivered on time and the cost of the warehouse is reduced. Besides, collaboration with the suppliers plays an instrumental role in reducing the lead time. The challenge, however, is that not all suppliers make a commitment to stock inventory that is needed by cement manufacturing firms.

Recommendations

The study established that top management supply support plays a positive helping role in improving the performance of cement manufacturing firms. Therefore, firms have to work collaboratively to serve the customers. Besides, the firms need to help the suppliers in training employees and shares some of the risks with their suppliers. Moreover, there should be an emphasis on continuous improvement.

Regarding lead time, it is crucial for organizations to focus on the reduction of the replenishment lead time from suppliers. Also, supplier collaboration needs to be encouraged since it enhances improved procurement performance. As well, it is of the essence for suppliers to make a commitment to stock an inventory of approved stock for each firm since it is a win-win situation for both the suppliers and the firms. This study recommends that another study be done to augment finding in this study. A comparative study across different industries might also be a more valuable contribution to this area of research. Moreover, the researcher has concluded that IT integration, top management supply support and lead time significantly relate to the performance of cement manufacturing firms, there is no evidence that performance is entirely dependent on the three independent variables. As such further research needs to be carried out to establish what other factors contribute significantly to the performance of cement manufacturing firms.

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